

AGRIGEP Final Conference

Rooting Sustainable Change: Inclusive Gender Equality Plans in Agriculture and Life Sciences Universities in Central and Eastern Europe

SAVE THE DATE
25 September 2025
Czech University of Life Sciences Prague

The Conference brings together researchers, educators, policy makers, and practitioners to reflect on Gender Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in higher education institutions across Europe, with a special focus on Central and Eastern Europe.

Why Attend?

- Actionable insights from real GEP implementation
- Diverse perspectives from academia, policy & practice
- Future pathways for inclusion in agri & life sciences
- Input into gender-responsive policy recommendations

Highlights

- Policy Roundtable: Advancing gender equality to boost EU competitiveness and innovation
- Keynote: Marcela Linková on shifting from formal compliance to true commitment
- Panel discussion 1: GEP 1.0 lessons & vision for GEP 2.0;
- Panel discussion 2: Sectoral strategies in agriculture & life sciences
- Poster Pitches: Spotlight on student and sister projects
- Call to Action: Driving inclusive transformation across European universities

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registration

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